

Sodium calcium silicate/chitosan composites for hard tissue applications

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Abstract : In this study, we have prepared bioactive sodium calcium silicate (SCS) powders from sodium carbonate, calcium nitrate, tetraethyl orthosilicate (TEOS) by sol-gel combustion method using citric acid as a fuel. Phase formation of the synthesized SCS powders was characterized by powder X-ray diffraction (XRD). Composites were prepared by adding different ratios of sodium calcium silicate powder to chitosan and their *in vitro* bioactivity was analyzed by immersing the composites in simulated body fluid (SBF) solution. Results show that more chitosan contain composite shows greater bioactivity when compared to the composites contains lesser chitosan. Estimation of calcium ion concentration in the SBF solution indicates that the calcium content present in the composite influences bioactivity.

Keywords : Sol-gel combustion, sodium calcium silicate, chitosan, bioactivity.

Introduction

Hydroxyapatite (HAP) is well studied for several years for biomedical applications because of its excellent bioactivity and osteoconductivity. However the poor mechanical properties (such as low fracture toughness) limit the scope of HAP in clinical applications. Recently, extensive research interest has been shown in development of silicon (Si) containing biomaterials for biomedical commitments particularly hard tissue regeneration applications. The advantage of silicates materials is their ability to release Si ions at concentrations that stimulates osteoblast cell growth and differentiation. These osteoblast cells are responsible for the extracellular matrix formation in bone¹⁻³. Calcium silicate ceramics such as larnite and wollastonite were already known for its bioactivity and biocompatibility characteristics. Similarly bioactive glasses are also studied intensively for hard tissue repair, due to their ability to form a chemical bond via apatite layer between bioactive glasses and natural tissues. In bioactive glasses silicon plays a major role in bioactivity and considered as a potential candidate for hard tissue repair. Moreover, alkali metal containing calcium silicates such as sodium calcium silicate having similar composition of bioactive glasses possess good bioactivity with basic Na₂O, CaO and SiO₂ components. Further, these sodium calcium silicates possess excellent mechanical properties⁴⁻⁶.

HAP/chitosan bioceramic composites show better

biomedical applications, since chitosan has hydrophilic surface, which helps in cell adhesion, proliferation and differentiation. Moreover, chitosan has cationic behavior along with good biocompatibility as well as better host response⁷⁻⁹. But sodium calcium silicate/chitosan (SCSC) composites are not well studied, which is expected to possess excellent bioactivity. In this study we prepared SCS powders by sol-gel combustion method and evaluated the HAP formation ability of their composites with chitosan.

Results and discussion

Synthesis and characterization :

In this sol-gel process the H⁺ ions from acid and OH⁻ ions from silanes combines and condensation reaction takes place through which gel was formed via polymeric network. The evolved high temperature during combustion helps for SCS phase formation. The dried gel was calcined at 700 °C and grinded, used for characterization. Fig. 1 shows the XRD pattern (obtained using Cu K α , Ni filtered radiation in powder-XRD instrument, Bruker, D8 Advance, Germany) of the synthesized SCS powders calcined at 700 °C for 4 h and resultant pattern was compared with reported pattern of the SCS powders with cubic crystal system (Na₂CaSiO₄, JCPDS file number : 096-101-0112). Particle size (*D*) of Na₂CaSiO₄ phase was calculated to be in the nano regime using Scherrer's for-

mula¹⁰ [$D = k\lambda/B \cos \theta$]. Along with $\text{Na}_2\text{CaSiO}_4$, secondary phase $\text{Na}_2\text{Ca}_2\text{Si}_2\text{O}_7$ was also observed in the XRD pattern (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. XRD pattern of SCS powder calcined at 700 °C for 4 h.

Bioactivity of the composites :

In vitro bioactivities of the composites were studied via apatite formation ability on their surface in SBF solution. The composites were soaked in the SBF at 37 °C by replacing SBF solution for every 24 h. Composite surfaces were examined using XRD after 4 days in order to check the deposition of HAP layer on their surfaces. For *in vitro* apatite formation studies two main factors (dissolution and precipitation) are influencing the interactions between SBF (i.e. physiological solution) and SCSC (i.e. bioactive composite material). In dissolution, the ions were released from composite, which were changing the ionic concentration and pH of the solution at the interface between composite/ SBF and then promotes the back precipitation of apatite layer on composite surface. These processes were observed when the amount of calcium ion concentration in the replaced SBF solution for every 24 h was estimated by ethylene diamine tetra acetic acid (EDTA) complexometric titration and the results were shown in the Fig. 3, which clearly supports the increase in the pH of the replaced SBF solution after 48 h is due the dissolution of calcium ions from the composites and later on the released ions concentration were decreased due to the deposition of calcite (CaCO_3) and HAP on the surface of the composites.

Fig. 2. XRD patterns of the composites after immersing in SBF for 4 days.

Fig. 3. Estimation of calcium ion released in SBF after immersion of composites.

XRD results of apatite formation ability of all composites in SBF solution after 4 days were shown in Fig. 2. After soaking in SBF, characteristic peaks of calcite was observed along with diffraction peaks of HAP, while the characteristic peaks of sodium calcium silicate were disappearing. Further, apatite precipitation on the surface of all the three composites differs from each other, where SC90 composite having the least apatite formation and SC70 possess higher apatite formation ability than other two composites. The compared XRD patterns of the composites clearly reveals that the apatite formation

increases with increasing chitosan content, in terms of decrease in the intensities or disappear of the calcite peaks. Thus SC70 composite shows more apatite formation compare to others, which indicates the significance of the chitosan in conjugation with SCS for hard tissue applications.

Moreover, the calcium ion release (Fig. 3) in the SBF solution from SC90 after 4 days was found to be at high concentration in comparison to that of SC80 and SC70. At the same time SC70 shows higher *in vitro* bioactivity when compared with other composites, which was observed from the XRD pattern.

Experimental

Synthesis of SCS powders and preparation of composites :

All chemicals were purchased commercially and used as such. SCS powders were prepared by sol-gel combustion method. At room temperature, sodium carbonate (1 M, 20 ml), calcium nitrate (1 M, 20 ml) and citric acid (1 M, 20 ml) were mixed thoroughly and then stoichiometric amount of TEOS was added, later 4 ml of concentrated HNO₃ was added, stirred for 7 h. Further, the solution was stirred for 4 h at 60 °C to form transparent gel. Thus formed gel was dried at 120 °C and combusted for 2 h at 500 °C and resulting product was pulverized and calcined at 700 °C for 4 h. Thus obtained powder and biopolymer were mixed thoroughly using mortar and pestle and composite discs were made by applying 7 tons of pressure in hydraulic pellet press with the composite disc diameter of 12 mm and thickness of 3 mm. Three composites were made of 90 : 10, 80 : 20, 70 : 30 ratios of sodium calcium silicate to chitosan and labeled as SC90, SC80 and SC70 respectively.

In vitro bioactivity of the composites :

SBF solution was prepared by using Kokubo method¹¹. *In vitro* bioactivity was investigated by immersing the composites in 15 ml of SBF at 37 °C in an incubator with the replacement of the simulated body fluid for every 24 h continuously for 4 days. The composites were removed on the fourth day, were dried at 60 °C for 30 min and surface of composites was analysed for HAP layer formation by using XRD.

The replaced SBF solution (15 ml) was titrated at the end of every 24 h to estimate the amount of released calcium ions concentration by EDTA method. 15 ml of this SBF solution was diluted to 100 ml. 10 ml of buffer solution and 3–4 drops of EBT indicator were added to the 20 ml of the above diluted solution and was titrated against 0.01 N EDTA solution. From the titre value Ca²⁺ concentration was estimated in SBF to estimate its loss due to the deposition of Ca²⁺ ions as HAP every day.

Conclusion

Sol-gel combustion process was employed to prepare sodium calcium silicate powders and their composites (sodium calcium silicate/chitosan) were made for hard tissue regeneration applications. All composites show the formation of HAP on their surface, along with calcite within 4 days, which proves that they possess good bioactivity. The composite with high concentration of chitosan possess better bioactivity compared with others.

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